

Digital Humanities Questionnaire, survey of humanities researchers' recognition and opinions on the digital humanities database——Educators' database

Xing Zhao, Shuning Li, Ya'nan Xiao, Haiqing Huang

1. If you study on an educator, which type of information do you need most? (multi-choices)

- A.Introduction B.Core educational view points C.Educator's works
D.Other people's comments and research E.Manuscripts F.Letters
G.Photos H.videos and audios I.Others _____

2. What contents do you think the Educator's Database should have?

- A.Chronology B.Autobiography C.Educator's works D.Biography
E.Other people's comments and research F.Others _____

3.What's your opinion on resources collection of Educator's Database?

- A.Collect all the resources about the educators B.Just collect the important resources about the educator

4.Do you think the authority of the resources of Educator's Database is important? (score from 1 star to 10 stars; 1 is "totally unimportant", 10 is "very important".)

Totally unimportant 1 star ☆☆☆☆☆☆☆☆☆☆ 10 stars Very important

5. If there are inconsistent information about the same thing(such as birth date), which do you want?

- A. Keep all the inconsistent information sources B.Just keep the relatively correct information sources C.Others _____

6. Do you want to get a tip on inconsistent information sources?

- A. Yes B.No

7. Do you think the visualization of Educator's Social Network is helpful to you?(see figure1, score from 1 star to 10 stars; 1 is "totally helpless", 10 is "very helpful".)

Figure1: Chen Heqin's Social Network Diagram

Totally helpless 1 star ☆☆☆☆☆☆☆☆☆☆ 10 stars Very helpful

8. Do you think the visualization of Educator's educational events is helpful to you?(see figure2, score from 1 star to 10 stars; 1 is "totally helpless", 10 is "very helpful".)

Figure 2: Colleges Founded By Ma Xiangbo

Totally helpless 1 star ☆☆☆☆☆☆☆☆☆☆ 10 stars Very helpful

9. Do you think the visualization of Educator's trajectory is helpful to you? (see figure3, score from 1 star to 10 stars; 1 is "totally helpless", 10 is "very helpful".)

Figure 3: Liang Shuming's Trajectory

Totally helpless 1 star ☆☆☆☆☆☆☆☆☆☆ 10 stars Very helpful

10. Do you think text mining of the Educator's educational thoughts is helpful to you?(score from 1 star to 10 stars; 1 is "totally helpless", 10 is "very helpful".)

Totally helpless 1 star ☆☆☆☆☆☆☆☆☆☆ 10 stars Very helpful

11. Do you think the timeline sort of Educator's works and marking the representative works is helpful to you?(score from 1 star to 10 stars; 1 is "totally helpless", 10 is "very helpful".)

Totally helpless 1 star ☆☆☆☆☆☆☆☆☆☆ 10 stars Very helpful

12. Have you heard of these databases?(multi-choices)

- A. CBDB
- B. Ctext
- C. Chinese People norm database
- D. Modern people of Hu'nan Province
- E. None

13. Have you heard of these following concepts?

- A. Digital humanities
- B. Prosopography
- C. GIS
- D. Python

E.Crowdsource F.None

14. Are you willing to accept relevant visualization training supplied by library?

A.Yes B.No

15. Are you willing to help correct and add information for library's database?

A.Yes B.No

16. Are you willing to share your resources with library to co-construct the database?

A.Yes B.No

17. During your study on educators, which problem is most difficult in information collecting and information processing?(filling in blank)

18. Which other function do you want the Educator's Database supply?(filling in blank)

19. What's your major?

A.Education B.History C.Others_____

20. What's your identity?

A.Faculty B.Ph.D. students C.Graduate students D.Undergraduate students
E.Others_____

21. Which province are you in?(filling in blank)
